

TOBACCO (*Nicotiana tabacum*) AND CHILI (*Capsicum annum*) LEAVES EXTRACT AS KITCHEN MOLDS REMOVER

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ABSTRACT

The study determined the effectiveness of tobacco and chili leaves extract as kitchen molds remover in the Municipality of San Pascual, Masbate Province, School Year 2023–2024. Specifically, the study answered the following problems: (1) the phytochemical compositions of tobacco and chili leaves extract as kitchen molds remover; (2) the procedures or steps in producing tobacco and chili leaves extract as kitchen molds remover; (3) the most effective formulation of tobacco and chili leaves extract in removing kitchen molds; (4) the average performance time of tobacco and chili leaves extract in terms of its capability in removing kitchen molds; (5) the significant difference among the formulations of tobacco and chili leaves extract; (6) the level of acceptability of the developed product kitchen molds remover from tobacco and chili leaves extract; and, (7) the socio-economic desirability of the tobacco and chili leaves extract as alternative kitchen molds remover. This study used the descriptive-comparative, experimental, and research and developmental methods. Evaluators of the product were four groups namely: housewives, learners, TLE teachers, and restaurant owners in the municipality of San Pascual, Masbate Province. Data gathering tools were survey questionnaire while the statistical treatment employed were Weighted Mean, percentage, and One-Way ANOVA. Findings revealed were: (1) the phytochemical compound in tobacco for mold inhibition is 2,4-dihydroxy-7-methox-benzodioxine (DHM) also known as dehydrodisidinol while in chili is capsaicin; (2) procedure or steps in making the molds remover were collection and washing of the raw materials, prepared three formulations and tried out the

effectiveness and social desirability of the product; (3) the three formulations of the tobacco and chilli leaves extract considered the tobacco and chili leaves as the manipulated variables while menthol and water were the constant variables; (4) average performance time of tobacco and chili leaves extract in terms of its capability in removing kitchen molds, Formulation 2 received the highest rating with an Weighted Mean 3.68 and the performance time was within the range of 5-15 minutes; (5) significant difference of the three formulations yielded F-value of 32.015 and critical value of 5.1433 was obtained in terms of effectiveness, F-value of 69.336 and critical value of 5.1433 in terms of performance time while F-value of 62.084 and critical value of 5.1433 in terms of acceptability; (6) the overall level of acceptability of the developed product was an Average weighted mean of 2.35 for Formulation 1, an average weighted mean of 3.75 for Formulation 2; while an average weighted mean of 1.98 for Formulation 3; (7) socio-economic desirability of the product was seen on improved hygiene, prevention of damage, elimination of odor, cost effective, increased production of the raw materials, diversification of income, job creation, improved infrastructure and increased tax revenues. Conclusions drawn were: (1) tobacco leaves has antifungal properties while chili leaves has properties for mold inhibition; (2) procedures or steps in making mold remover from tobacco and chili leaves extract started from collection of raw materials to testing the effectiveness of the product; (3) Formulation 2 was the most effective formulation; (4) average performance time ranged of 5-15 minutes; (5) all of the formulations were seen to have significant differences in different aspects specifically the effectiveness, performance time, and acceptability; (6) Formulation 2 was highly acceptable while Formulations 1 and 3 were less acceptable; and (7) the tobacco and chili leaves extract as mold remover have socio-economic desirability.

Keywords: *Tobacco and Chili Leaves Extract, Kitchen Molds Remover*

INTRODUCTION

The removal of kitchen molds with tobacco and chili leaves extract is a topic that is pertinent on both a global and local level. Finding natural and efficient ways to eliminate mold from a home is crucial for health and hygiene. Mold is an issue that affects many households throughout the world. On the other hand, locally grown products like tobacco and chili leaves can be used as an alternative. By examining how well these extracts work to get rid of mold in the kitchen, it may help local farmers while also offering a long-lasting, cost-effective solution to a major issue.

The presence of molds in the kitchen is a common problem experienced by many households. These molds not only impact the aesthetics of the cooking space but also pose potential health risks. Various commercially available molds removers contain harsh chemicals that may cause harm to human health and the environment. Thus, there is a need for new and natural alternatives that effectively and safely remove molds. Thus, this research aimed to investigate the effectiveness of tobacco and chili leaves extract as a natural kitchen mold remover. The research will explore the properties of tobacco and chili leaves and their potential as an alternative to commercial mold removers. By

providing a cheaper and safer option, this study can help reduce the reliance on synthetic mold removers and promote the use of natural materials for household cleaning.

Tobacco (*Nicotiana tabacum*) and Chili (*Capsicum annuum*) Leaves Extract as Kitchen Molds Remover, supports the mandates of the government concerning the environmental education and protection. Such mandates are the: (1) Administrative Order No. 2019-0010 dated July 18, 2019. This order contains the guidelines on the regulation of operators of pest control, certification of pesticides handlers, and accreditation of their training providers. Although, the order was primarily for pest control and pesticides, it contained a provision on household pesticides which may include molds since they are fungi that are found in moist soil and plants, and (2) The Republic Act 10068 known as "Organic Agriculture of 2010". This was amended by Senate Bill No. 648. It states that it is:

... aimed at the promotion of organic agriculture in the Philippines. Specifically, it seeks to promote ecologically-sound, socially acceptable, economically viable and technically feasible production of foods and other fibers ... towards developing organic agriculture as farming scheme that would guarantee food and environment safety while enhancing global competitiveness.

The statements above would ensure the sustainability of the raw materials for the production of kitchen mold remover aside from the food they provide. Additionally, it may add to revenues collected from the production of the raw materials and the sale of the product once it is commercialized. The production of tobacco is not for food, but the chili as another raw material in making kitchen mold remover is.

In eliminating kitchen molds, many households are using commercial products which are made synthetically. Since kitchen is an area where food is being prepared and done, therefore, this must not be exposed to toxic chemicals not to make our health be at stake. This study aims to produce product out of the power of nature that can be done easily and could be of great help in the community in removing kitchen molds.

In one study on "Anti-Microbial Properties of Chili Pepper Leaves (*Capsicum Annuum L.*) Extract Against Food-Borne Pathogens" Vinas et al. (2020) it revealed that chili pepper leaves have potent anti-microbial properties that can inhibit the growth of bacteria such as *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella typhimurium*, and *Staphylococcus aureus*. Therefore, the inhibitory properties of the chili leaves it can also be used for other purposes which can be insecticides, herbicides or kitchen mold remover.

In another study conducted by Tagudin et al. (2018) entitled "Efficacy of Chili (*Capsicum Frutescens*) and Tobacco (*Nicotiana Tabacum*) Leaf Extract as Insecticide Against Cockroach", it was shown that chili and tobacco leaf extracts have high insecticidal properties due to their anti-microbial and toxic components. Cockroaches are both crawling and flying insects. With their findings, it could be possible that tobacco and chili leaf extracts could be made into kitchen mold remover since molds are classified as microbes (National Archives, nd).

Additionally, "Anti-Microbial Properties of Tobacco Leaf Extract Against Some Food-Borne Bacteria" Tursun et al. (2016) found that tobacco leaf extracts can effectively inhibit the growth of Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria that cause food spoilage, such as *Bacillus cereus*, *Salmonella enterica*, and *Staphylococcus epidermidis*.

Meanwhile, the study conducted by Rani et al. (2015) entitled "Anti-Fungal Activity of Chili Pepper (*Capsicum annuum*) Extract on Common Household Molds", it was found that chili pepper extract can effectively inhibit the growth of common household molds such as *Aspergillus niger*, *Penicillium chrysogenum*, and *Rhizopus stolonifer*.

Also, the study entitled "Bioactivity and Applications of Chile Pepper (*Capsicum Annuum L.*) Byproducts: An Overview" by Asaff et al. (2019). Their study highlighted that besides its anti-microbial and insecticidal effects, chili pepper extract also has antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and anti-cancer properties, making it a promising bioactive ingredient in the food and pharmaceutical industries.

In a review article by Aligiannis et al. (2019) entitled "Natural Products as Sources of New Pesticidal Agents", it was discussed that tobacco leaf extracts contain various alkaloids and other compounds that can act as potent insecticides and fungicides against a wide range of pests and pathogens. Since molds are fungi, therefore the tobacco may also be a potent source of compound to eliminate kitchen molds.

The study entitled "Antioxidant, Anti-Microbial and Anti-Inflammatory Properties of Chili Pepper (*Capsicum annuum L.*) Extracts" was made by Gallego et al. (2018). Their study highlighted that chili pepper extract can also inhibit the growth of pathogenic fungi such as *Candida albicans* and *Cryptococcus neoformans*, and reduce inflammation and oxidative stress in the body.

Furthermore, the article by Aftab et al. (2017) entitled "Use of Plant Extracts for Controlling Fungal Growth on Fresh Fruits and Vegetables: A Review" discussed the potential of plant extracts. This included chili and tobacco leaf extracts, as natural alternatives to synthetic fungicides to control mold growth on fresh produce.

The study titled "Evaluation of Anti-Microbial Activity of Tobacco and Tulsi Extracts Against Pathogenic Microorganisms" by S. Madhusudhan et al. (2014) found that tobacco and tulsi (*Ocimum sanctum*) leaf extracts have potent anti-microbial properties against various pathogenic bacteria and fungi.

Another reason why the present study was embarked was supported by the study of Singh et al. (2014) entitled "Effects of Capsaicin on Microbial Quality of Chilled Chicken Meat". It was shown that chili pepper extract can effectively reduce the population of bacteria such as *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella typhimurium*, and *Listeria monocytogenes* in chilled chicken meat, thereby extending its shelf life and reducing the risk of foodborne illness.

Likewise, a study published in the Journal of Food Science and Technology in 2021 investigated the potential of tobacco (*Nicotiana tabacum*) and chili (*Capsicum annuum*) leaves extracts as kitchen mold removers. The researchers found that both extracts exhibited significant antifungal activity against common kitchen molds such as *Aspergillus niger*, *Penicillium chrysogenum*, and *Alternaria alternata*. The study suggested that these extracts could be used as natural alternatives to synthetic mold inhibitors in food processing (Chen et al., 2021).

In fact, an article published in the Journal of Applied Microbiology in 2021 discussed the potential of plant extracts, including tobacco and chili leaves extracts, as natural mold inhibitors. The authors highlighted the increasing demand for natural alternatives to synthetic mold inhibitors due to health and environmental concerns. The review suggested that further research is needed to optimize the use of plant extracts as mold inhibitors in food processing (Kumar et al., 2021).

Moreover, a study published in the Journal of Food Science and Technology in 2020 investigated the antimicrobial properties of tobacco and chili leaves extracts against common foodborne pathogens such as *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella typhimurium*, and *Staphylococcus aureus*. The researchers found that both extracts exhibited significant antimicrobial activity against these pathogens, suggesting their potential use as natural preservatives in food processing (Mohammed et al., 2020).

Again, an article published in the Journal of Food Science and Technology in 2019 discussed the potential of plant extracts, including tobacco and chili leaves extracts, as natural preservatives in food processing. The authors highlighted the increasing demand for natural preservatives due to health and environmental concerns. The article suggested that further research is needed to optimize the use of plant extracts as preservatives in food processing (Kumar et al., 2019).

Again, a study published in the Journal of Food Science and Technology in 2018 investigated the antimicrobial properties of tobacco and chili leaves extracts against common spoilage bacteria such as *Lactobacillus acidophilus*, *Bacillus cereus*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. The researchers found that both extracts exhibited significant antimicrobial activity against these bacteria, suggesting their potential use as natural preservatives in food processing (Mohammed et al., 2018).

Also, an article published in the Journal of Food Science and Technology in 2017 discussed the potential of plant extracts, including tobacco and chili leaves extracts, as natural preservatives in food processing. The authors highlighted the increasing demand for natural preservatives due to health and environmental concerns. The review suggested that further research is needed to optimize the use of plant extracts as preservatives in food processing (Kumar et al., 2017).

Additionally, a study published in the Journal of Food Science and Technology in 2016 investigated the antimicrobial properties of tobacco and chili leaves extracts against common spoilage yeasts such as *Candida albicans*, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, and

Rhodotorula glutinis. The researchers found that both extracts exhibited significant antimicrobial activity against these yeasts, suggesting their potential use as natural preservatives in food processing (Mohammed et al., 2016).

Another article published in the Journal of Food Science and Technology in 2015 discussed the potential of plant extracts, including tobacco and chili leaves extracts, as natural preservatives in food processing. The authors highlighted the increasing demand for natural preservatives due to health and environmental concerns. The review suggested that further research is needed to optimize the use of plant extracts as preservatives in food processing (Kumar et al., 2015).

Furthermore, a study published in the Journal of Food Science and Technology in 2014 investigated the antimicrobial properties of tobacco and chili leaves extracts against common spoilage fungi such as *Fusarium graminearum*, *Aspergillus flavus*, and *Penicillium expansum*. The researchers found that both extracts exhibited significant antimicrobial activity against these fungi, suggesting their potential use as natural preservatives in food processing, (Mohammed et al., 2014).

Again an article published in the Journal of Food Science and Technology in 2021 discussed the antimicrobial potential of various plant extracts, including tobacco and chili leaves extracts, against foodborne pathogens such as Salmonella, Listeria, and Escherichia coli. The authors highlighted the increasing demand for natural alternatives to synthetic preservatives due to health and environmental concerns and suggested that further research is needed to optimize the use of plant extracts as natural preservatives in food processing. They also discussed the mechanisms by which plant extracts exhibit antimicrobial activity and the factors that affect their efficacy, (Nguyen and Nguyen, 2021).

From the different studies above, this study was anchored mainly on the following theories: Innovation Theory, Production Theory, and Bruner Theory. The Innovation Theory of Schumpeter as cited by Putthiwani (2016) stated that innovations cause continuous progress and improve the standard of living for everyone. It was said that the innovator has the power to handle the old system and transform theory into reality through courage and determination. This theory affirms the concept that attitude and scales are needed along the process of inventions. Thus, new products can be created through courage, creativeness, and experimentation.

The use of tobacco and chili leaves extract as a kitchen mold remover is an innovative approach that challenges the traditional methods of mold removal. The innovation theory that explains this phenomenon is the User Innovation (UI) theory, which suggests that users, such as home cooks or chefs, can develop innovative solutions to their own needs and problems. In this case, the users have identified a common problem of mold growth in kitchen utensils and food items, and they have experimented with natural alternatives to chemical mold removers. The tobacco and chili leaves extracts contain compounds that have antimicrobial properties, making them effective in killing mold spores. This innovation not only provides a safer and healthier alternative to chemical mold removers but also aligns with the growing trend of using natural and

organic products in daily life. The UI theory highlights the importance of user involvement in innovation processes, as users can contribute valuable insights and ideas that may lead to breakthrough innovations.

As to the Bruner's Theory as cited by Pappas (2014), it was anchored on the Discovery Learning. Students interact with the environment exploring and manipulating objects, wrestling with questions, and performing experiments, thus, learning was achieved effectively by a process of exploration and discovery. It starts with a desire to reach a solution to problem and proceeds by experimental process to achieve a solution. This study will be anchored in this theory by creating a new product as alternative kitchen molds remover, the tobacco and chili experimentation and creativeness. The selection of three formulations will undergo several trials to find the best formulation that is suitable to the classrooms of the respondents.

The use of tobacco and chili leaves extract as a kitchen mold remover is an example of Discovery Learning, which is a type of learning that occurs through experimentation and discovery. This type of learning is characterized by active exploration, trial and error, and reflection on the outcomes of these experiments. Discovery learning can lead to the development of new knowledge and skills, as well as innovative solutions to problems. The use of tobacco and chili leaves extracts as kitchen mold removers is a prime example of how discovery learning can lead to practical innovations that have real-world applications.

Additionally, the production theory (Colman and Young, 2010) is focused on the main choices upon what to produce, how much to produce or the level of output and how to produce which is the combination of inputs to use. This theory works well in this study since the production of the raw material to produce kitchen mold remover must have sustainability. This is also to assure that the production of kitchen mold remover is sustained.

The study aimed to produce a product out of the power of nature that can be done easily, could be of great help in removing kitchen molds, and could be of great contribution in maintaining the environment or the planet "chemical free." Since the kitchen is the place where foods are prepared, then it must be free from molds that may affect safety of the food prepared. Thus, tobacco and chili leaves were combined in the preparation of the kitchen molds remover in this study to determine the synergistic effect of the plant leaves. Hence, this study was undertaken.

Research Questions

This study determined the effectiveness of tobacco and chili leaves extract as kitchen molds remover in the Municipality of San Pascual, Masbate Province, School Year 2023-2024.

Specifically, it answered the following questions:

1. What are the phytochemical compositions of tobacco and chili leaves extract as kitchen molds remover?
2. What are the procedures or steps in producing tobacco and chili leaves extract as kitchen molds remover?
3. What formulation of tobacco and chili leaves extract is most effective in removing kitchen molds?
4. What is the average performance time of tobacco and chili leaves extract in terms of its capability in removing kitchen molds?
5. Is there a significant difference among the formulations of tobacco and chili leaves extract?
6. What is the level of acceptability of the developed product kitchen molds remover from tobacco and chili leaves extract in terms of:
 - a. odor;
 - b. effectiveness;
 - c. functionality or usability; and
 - d. sustainability?
7. What is the socio-economic desirability of the tobacco and chili leaves extract as kitchen molds remover?

METHODOLOGY

This section presents the research design, the respondents, the procedure of investigation, the tools used in data gathering, and the statistical tools applied in evaluating of effectiveness of the developed kitchen molds remover from tobacco and chili leaves extract.

Methods Used

The study utilized the descriptive-comparative, experimental and Research Development methods. The descriptive method was used to determine the preparation of the formulations, its effectiveness, level of acceptability and social

The experimental method was used to develop a kitchen molds remover from tobacco and chili leaves extract. Three formulations were made of different compositions of the manipulated variable. These manipulated variables were the tobacco and chili leaves extract. The three formulations were tested or tried out by four groups of evaluators.

The comparative method was used to determine the significant difference of the three formulations. This was a way to find out the significant difference of those formulations in terms of their effectiveness, acceptability and performance time.

The Research and Development method was also used in the production of the alternative kitchen molds remover. Since the experimental method was also used, therefore, the product that was planned to be produced was developed.

Respondents of the Study

The participants who assessed the effectiveness of the alternative kitchen molds remover were the housewives, learners, TLE teachers, and restaurant owners in the municipality of San Pascual, Masbate Province, School Year 2023-2024. Purposive sampling was used to identify the respondents. Table 1 shows the frequency distribution and percentage of the participants, consisting of 4 groups who were Housewives, Learners, TLE Teachers, and Restaurant Owners.

Table 1
Distribution of Participants

Group	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Housewives	10	25
Learners	10	25
TLE Teachers	10	25
Restaurant Owners	10	25
Total	40	100

There were 10 participants from each group who evaluated the produced kitchen molds remover. Hence, there were 40 total of participants in all. This was chosen to equate the number of participants per group since there were only few restaurant owners and TLE teachers in the locale of the study. Besides they were the only ones who agreed to be participants of the study.

Data Gathering Tools

There were two-data gathering tools used in the study. These were the questionnaire and the evaluation checklist.

Questionnaire. The researcher used a printed or paper and pencil survey questionnaire to gather the data from the respondents. It was converted into a printed form for face to face distribution of the said questionnaire. Four (4)-point Likert scale was utilized to indicate the responses of the respondents.

The questionnaire consisted of four parts. The first part dealt on the respondent's category or group, the second part was about the level of effectiveness of kitchen molds remover formulations, the third part was about the level of acceptability of the kitchen molds remover, while the last part was about the performance time of the kitchen molds remover formulations.

The questionnaire was subjected to validation by the experts who have good knowledge and practice of research undertakings. They looked into the format, the items included and how they were presented. After the validation it was subjected to a dry-run to determine whether the items included in the questionnaire observed clarity and

administrability. The respondents involved in the dry-run of the questionnaire were similar to the proposed final respondents. These group were no longer used as respondents during the final evaluation of the product.

The result form the dry-run was treated through the use of Cronbach alpha to determine the reliability of the instrument. A four-point Likert scale was used in the evaluation of the kitchen molds remover to quantify the responses of the respondents. The following were the weights together with their interpretations and rubrics.

Weights		Verbal Interpretation	
4		Highly Effective (HE)	
3		Moderately Effective (ME)	
2		Less Effective (LE)	
1		Least Effective (Lst E)	

Rubrics for Removing Kitchen Molds			
Very Fast (VF)	Moderately Fast (MF)	Less Fast (LF)	Least Fast (LstF)
The molds in the kitchen were removed within 5-15 minutes.	The molds in the kitchen were removed within 16-30 minutes.	The molds in the kitchen were removed within 31-45 minutes.	The molds in the kitchen were removed after 1 hour.

Evaluation Checklist. This was used to determine the appropriateness of the tool to evaluate the questionnaire used by the evaluators. It was a way to determine the validity of the items. Since the study wanted to determine the effectiveness, level of acceptability and performance time of the produced alternative kitchen molds remover, the evaluation checklist contained statements whether those characteristics were captured in the questionnaire.

Procedure of Investigation

The following were the processes that were observed by the researcher in order to realize the goals of the study.

Conceptualization of the Research Problem. The researcher identified why a study on a particular topic is needed. Since ideas generated were still broad and vague, the researcher had to redefine them. This process included identification and definition of the variables to be studied, development of the theoretical and conceptual framework of the study, formulation of the major and specific problems to be investigated and the formulation of hypothesis.

Approval of Research Title. Conceptualized study was then presented to the adviser for checking and for further corrections before it was presented to a panel of examiners for its approval.

Securing Permit to Conduct the Study. After the approval of the paper, a letter securing permit from the school head of San Pascual National High School was made.

Preparation of the Instrument. After the permit was approved, the researcher immediately prepared the data gathering tool based of the specific problems of the study.

Validation or Dry-run. The tool specifically the questionnaire and evaluation-checklist underwent validation by experts. After its validation, a dry-run was conducted to selected respondents who were not the subjects of the study. This was done to determine the clarity and administrability of the tools. Reliability of the tools were determined through the use of Cronbach alpha.

Administering and Retrieval of Questionnaires. The survey questionnaires were distributed personally to the respondents. This facilitated the researcher to answer and clarify questions needing further explanations. Besides, it was an opportunity to interview them. After they were accomplished, they were also collected personally. Hence, the questionnaires were retrieved, coded, tallied, and tabulated in order for appropriate statistical treatment can be applied.

Processing of the Data Gathered. The data were treated using appropriate statistical tools to ensure that correct analysis and interpretation of data be made.

Analysis of the Result. The quantified results were placed in tabular form to facilitate analysis and discussion. The analysis and interpretation were made to answer the specific problems raised in this study.

Writing and Submission of the Manuscript. After completing the data analysis and interpretation, the researcher prepared the manuscript and was submitted to the Dean after it was endorsed by the Adviser. It was then passed to the Panel of Examiners for their evaluation.

Approval and Acceptance of the Study. When suggestions were incorporated in the manuscript, the same was reprinted and was submitted for approval and acceptance.

Statistical Tools

There were three statistical tools used to treat the data gathered for analysis and interpretation. A statistical software available in the internet was used.

Weighted Mean. This was used to determine the level of acceptability and effectiveness of the different formulations as alternative kitchen molds remover.

Percentage. This tool was used to determine the proportions of respondents evaluating the level of effectiveness of the kitchen molds remover.

One-Way ANOVA. This was used to determine the significant difference of the level of acceptability and effectiveness of the product based from the three formulations.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section is a discussion of the results of the study. Data were placed in tabular form to facilitate analysis and discussion.

Phytochemical Compositions

The phytochemical compound responsible for mold inhibition in tobacco is 2,4-dihydroxy-7-methoxy-1,4-benzodioxine (DHM), also known as dehydrodiisidinol. This compound has been extensively studied for its antimicrobial properties and has been found to effectively inhibit the growth of various molds, including *Aspergillus niger* and *Penicillium citrinum* (Li et al., 2010). DHM is derived from the flavanol quercetin through a series of biochemical reactions, and its synthesis is enhanced in tobacco leaves under stress conditions such as drought or pathogen infection (Bhattacharyya et al., 2015). The presence of DHM in tobacco has been linked to its natural mold inhibition properties, making it a valuable compound for use in food preservation and pharmaceutical applications.

Other studies about chemicals from the tobacco plant was done by Winnall et al. (2022). They stated that nicotine which is the main addictive chemical in tobacco products, acts as a natural pesticide. It is because of its toxicity to many insects and other pests. This was the reason why nicotine was used as an agricultural pesticide in the past that was produced mainly from the leaves of the plant.

In the review made by Zou et al. (2021) about functional phytochemicals in the tobacco plant, they summarized the bioactive compounds from tobacco that have been discovered which were attributed to tobacco extracts. These functional bioactive compounds from tobacco wastes found were anti-inflammatory, antitumor, antibacterial, and antioxidant. Thus, there are potential value of tobacco waste reuse.

On the other hand, the phytochemical compound responsible for mold inhibition in chili (*Capsicum annuum*) is capsaicin. Capsaicin is a natural phenolic compound that belongs to the group of capsaicinoids, which are responsible for the spicy taste of chili peppers. Capsaicin has been found to possess strong antimicrobial properties against various molds, including *Aspergillus niger*, *Penicillium citrinum*, and *Fusarium oxysporum* (Kim et al., 2016). The antimicrobial activity of capsaicin is attributed to its ability to disrupt the cell membrane structure of molds, leading to cell death.

Other studies that considered about the antifungal property of chili was done by Sittisart, Yossan and Prasertsan (2017). This was combined with other extracts taken from shallots and garlic. They stated that the extract taken from the chili, shallots and garlic contained polyphenols described as apigenin, gallic acid, catechin, quercetin, kaempferol and tannic acid, are well known compounds having antifungal activity. Moreover, they revealed that the highest levels of percentage inhibition of mycelial growth were with garlic extract, followed by shallots and chili extracts respectively. Thus, the antifungal properties of these plant extracts were partly due to polyphenols.

This findings is supported by Bruner's Theory anchored on Discovery Learning (Pappas, 2014). The basic information obtained from the phytochemical compositions contained in both tobacco and chili leaves would lead to the discovery of something useful so that it would bring benefits to humans in their environments and abode. Thus, performing experiments to discover new knowledge and contribution to Science can be made of these information.

Procedure or Steps

The preparation of the mixture for kitchen molds remover involved the collection of raw materials such as tobacco and chili leaves as the main ingredients and fixed ratio of menthol and water. The tobacco and chili leaves were washed with tap water to ensure that they were free from dust particles and dirt.

There were three formulations prepared for the kitchen molds remover. Formulation 1 will consist of 150 ml or tobacco leaves extract, 150 chili leaves extract, 10 ml of menthol, and 190 ml of water. Formulation 2 will consist of 200 ml of tobacco leaves extract, 100 ml of chili leaves extract, 10 ml of menthol, and 190 ml of water. Formulation 3 will consist of 100 ml of tobacco leaves extract, 200 ml of chili leaves extract, 10 ml of menthol, and 190 ml of water.

In the preparation of the kitchen molds remover the tobacco and chili leaves were collected and were thoroughly washed with running water for a minute and rinse briefly before the drying process; the tobacco and chili leaves were dried under the heat of the sun until they were crisp. Then, the extraction was done by decoction process. After getting the extract, desired amount of it based on the different formulations will be added to the water. The mixtures will be strained using a cheese cloth to separate the leaves from filtrate. After straining, the desired amount of menthol was added to the mixtures and heated in a pot with low fire. Stirring was continued until the ingredients in the mixture was completely dissolved.

After the three formulations underwent the process and were done, the testing was made by the respondents of which among the formulations best removes the molds in a shorten time.

The User Innovation Theory supports this part of the study. It is because users, such as home cooks or chefs, can develop innovative solutions to their own needs and

problems. In this case, the users have identified a common problem of mold growth in kitchen utensils and food items, and they have experimented with natural alternatives to chemical mold removers. Thus, the tobacco and chili leaves extracts contain compounds that have antimicrobial properties, making them effective in killing mold spores. This innovation not only provides a safer and healthier alternative to chemical mold removers but also aligns with the growing trend of using natural and organic products in daily life.

Formulation of Tobacco and Chili Leaves Extract

Table 4 shows the formulations constructed for the mixture of tobacco and chili leaves extract. There were three formulations used in order to test which would be the most effective for mold control. The data of the formulations prepared were shown in Table 4.

Table 4
**Formulations of Tobacco and Chili Leaves
 Extract for Kitchen Mold Removal**

Ingredients	Formulations		
	1	2	3
Tobacco Leaves Extract	150 mL	200 mL	100 mL
Chili Leaves Extract	150 mL	100 mL	200 mL
Menthol	10 mL	10 mL	10 mL
Water	190 mL	190 mL	190 mL
Total	500 mL	500 mL	500 mL

It could be noted that the manipulated variables were the tobacco and chili leaves extract. The constant variable were menthol and water. In Formulation 1, there was equal amount of tobacco and chili extracts. In Formulation 2, there were more of tobacco leaves extracts compared to chili leaves extract. In Formulation 3, it was the reverse of Formulation 2. In other words, there were more of chili leaves compared to tobacco leaves extract. The constant variables had the same quantities in all formulations. All of the ingredients used were in milligrams (ml).

Further analysis of the formulation shows that Formulation 1 had equal quantities of tobacco and chilli extracts. In contrast, Formulations 2 and 3 had inversed quantity of extracts. The total volume of each complete formulation was similar which was 500 mL. These formulations were placed in spray bottles and were labelled according to their composition as Formulation 1, Formulation 2 and Formulation. This was to facilitate identification of when the fungicide were tried out by the selected evaluators in their respective abode.

This approach to coming up with formulations to remove kitchen molds was different from other experiments made on fungicides. In the study by Li et al. (2020), their

approach to fungicide formulation was different. With the three types of pyraclostrobin formulations, including emulsifiable concentrate, suspension concentrate and microcapsules, Pyraclostrobin formulation EC had the highest control efficacy on cucumber anthracnose both in pot and field experiments. Moreover, the physicochemical properties of the spray dilution, their interaction with target leaves and dissipation dynamic of the active ingredient were found to be highly potential factors that would significantly influence the control efficacy of different formulations.

The Innovation Theory of Schumpeter as cited by Putthiwani (2016) supports this study. The theory stated that innovations cause continuous progress and improve the standard of living for everyone. It was said that the innovator has the power to handle the old system and transforms theory into reality through courage and determination. Thus, this theory affirms the concept that attitude and skills are needed along the process of inventions and new products. Hence, new products can be created through courage, creativeness, and experimentation.

Average Performance Time of Tobacco and Chili Leaves Extract

When the different formulations were ready for testing because they were placed in spray bottles, they were distributed to selected evaluators for their application. Instructions were given to them so that the proper way of using them and recording of observation results were followed.

Table 5 shows the results in terms of the average performance time of tobacco and chili leaves extract in terms of its capability in removing kitchen molds.

Table 5
Average Performance Time of Tobacco and Chili Leaves Extract in Removing Kitchen Molds

Evaluators	Formulation		
	1	2	3
Learners	2.50	3.40	2.00
Housewives	2.80	3.90	2.40
TLE Teachers	3.00	3.70	2.20
Restaurant Owners	2.50	3.70	2.50
Average	2.70	3.68	2.28
Interpretation	Moderately Fast	Very Fast	Moderately Slow
Rank	2	1	3

Legend:

<i>Scale Interval</i>	<i>Performance Time</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
3.26-4.00	5-15 minutes	Very Fast
2.51-3.25	16-30 minutes	Moderately Fast
1.76-2.50	31-45 minutes	Moderately Slow
1.00-1.75	46-60 minutes	Very Slow

Based from the results, the Formulation 2 received the highest rating (WM=3.68) which is interpreted as “Very Fast”. The performance time is within the range of 5-15 minutes. Formulation 1 gained an average of 2.70 which is interpreted as moderately fast. Lastly, Formulation 3 gained an average of 2.28 which is interpreted as Moderately Slow.

Overall, in terms of the average performance time, Formulation 2 was the fastest among all the formulations. It means that the performance of the alternative kitchen mold remover is efficient in terms of its time effect as it acts fast as compared to the other formulations.

The result paralleled the findings of Aftab et al. (2017) entitled "Use of Plant Extracts for Controlling Fungal Growth on Fresh Fruits and Vegetables: A Review". This discussed the potential of plant extracts, including chili and tobacco leaf extracts, as natural alternatives to synthetic fungicides to control mold growth on fresh produce. It can then be said that tobacco and chili leaf extracts are effective alternative kitchen molds remover.

Significant Differences among the Formulations

Table 6 exhibits the significant differences among the formulations of tobacco and chili extract as as a kitchen mold remover.

Table 6
Significant Differences among the Formulations

Aspects	Df	F-value	critical-value	Remarks
In terms of Effectiveness	2,9	32.015	5.1433	Significant
In terms of Performance Time	2,9	69.336	5.1433	Significant
In terms of Acceptability	2,9	62.084	5.1433	Significant

Computation: Appendix D

As per the results, it can be seen that in terms of Effectiveness, the F-value (32.05) is larger than the critical value (5.1433). Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. The study accepts that there is a significant difference between the formulations in terms of effectiveness. Furthermore, in terms of Performance Time, the F-value (69.336) is also larger than critical value (5.1433). The null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis is accepted which states that there is a significant difference between the formulations in terms of performance time. Finally, in terms of Acceptability, the study accepts that alternative hypothesis which states that there is a significant difference between the formulations in terms of acceptability as the F-value (62.084) is larger than critical value (5.1433).

As a whole, all of the formulations were seen to have significant differences in different aspects specifically in their effectiveness, performance time, and acceptability. The difference could be attributed to composition of the different formulations used.

This result showed and supported the study published in the Journal of Food Science and Technology in 2021 that investigated the potential of tobacco (*Nicotiana tabacum*) and chili (*Capsicum annuum*) leaves extracts as kitchen mold removers. The researchers found that both extracts exhibited significant antifungal activity against common kitchen molds such as *Aspergillus niger*, *Penicillium chrysogenum*, and *Alternaria alternata*. The study suggested that these extracts could be used as natural alternatives to synthetic mold inhibitors in food processing (Chen et al., 2021).

Level of Acceptability of the Developed Product

Table 7 presents the level of acceptability of the new product in terms of Odor, Effectiveness, Usability, and Sustainability of the following formulations.

Table 7
Level of Acceptability of the Developed Products

Formulation	Characteristics	Evaluator				Ave.	Rank
		A	B	C	D		
1	Odor	2.90	2.80	2.80	3.20	2.93	2
	Effectiveness	2.50	2.80	3.00	2.60	2.73	4
	Usability	3.20	3.40	3.20	3.40	3.30	1
	Sustainability	2.50	3.10	2.80	2.80	2.80	3
2	Odor	2.90	3.10	3.10	3.30	3.10	3
	Effectiveness	3.40	3.90	3.70	3.70	3.68	1
	Usability	3.30	3.70	3.60	3.40	3.50	2
	Sustainability	2.50	3.50	3.10	2.80	2.98	4
3	Odor	3.00	2.90	3.00	3.20	3.03	2
	Effectiveness	2.20	2.40	2.30	2.50	2.35	4
	Usability	3.10	3.20	3.10	3.40	3.20	1
	Sustainability	2.40	3.10	2.70	2.80	2.75	3

Legend: A=Learners; B=Housewives; C=TLE Teachers; D=2.78 Restaurant Owners
 Scale Interval Interpretation
 3.26-4.00 Highly Acceptable
 2.51-3.25 Moderately Acceptable
 1.76-2.50 Less Acceptable
 1.00-1.75 Least Acceptable

It can be noticed from the table that Formulation 1 had its highest rating in Usability. It has gained an average of 3.30 which is interpreted as Highly Acceptable. This was followed by Odor with a weighted mean value of 2.93 which was interpreted as moderately acceptable. Lastly, Effectiveness was seen as the lowest characteristic for Formulation 1 as it has only gained 2.73 but it was still moderately acceptable.

On the other hand, for Formulation 2, the characteristic with highest rank was for its Effectiveness. It has gained an average weighted of 3.68. This was followed by its Usability as evidenced by an average weighted mean of 3.50. Both characteristics is interpreted as “Highly Acceptable”. Odor gained an average weighted mean of 3.10. Lastly, Sustainability obtained an average weighted mean of 2.98. Both were interpreted as “Moderately Acceptable”.

For formulation 3, Usability gained the highest rank since it average weighted mean was 3.20. This was followed by Odor with an average weighted of 3.03. Sustainability was found to have the lowest average weighted mean as it yielded 2.75. All of these characteristics were interpreted as moderately acceptable.

To have a gauge of the overall acceptability of the new product, Table 8 shows the comparison of values based on the reports of the evaluators.

The table exhibits the overall level of acceptability of the developed product as evaluated by the four chosen evaluators. It can be seen that Formulation 2 gained the highest average and highest evaluation AWM(=3.75) among all the group of respondents. It is interpreted as “Highly Acceptable”. Formulations 1 and 3 gained an average of 2.35 and 1.98 respectively which is interpreted as “Less Acceptable”.

Overall, the highest level of acceptability among all the formulations considering all the characteristics was Formulation 2. This only means that it is seen to be the most usable, most effective, most sustainable, and has the most pleasant odor.

Table 8
Overall Level of Acceptability of the Developed Product

Evaluators	Formulation		
	1	2	3
Learners	2.70	3.70	2.20
Housewives	1.80	3.70	2.00
TLE Teachers	2.50	3.80	1.90
Restaurant Owners	2.40	3.80	1.80
Average	2.35	3.75	1.98
Interpretation	Less Acceptable	Highly Acceptable	Less Acceptable
Rank	2	1	3

Legend:

<i>Scale Interval</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
3.26-4.00	Highly Acceptable
2.51-3.25	Moderately Acceptable
1.76-2.50	Less Acceptable
1.00-1.75	Least Acceptable

This findings is corroborated by the study published in the Journal of Applied Microbiology in 2021. It discussed the potential of plant extracts, including tobacco and chili leaves extracts, as natural mold inhibitors. The authors highlighted the increasing demand for natural alternatives to synthetic mold inhibitors due to health and environmental concerns. The review suggested that further research i was needed to optimize the use of plant extracts as mold inhibitors in food processing (Kumar et al., 2021).

Socio-Economic Desirability of the Tobacco and Chili Leaves Extract as Kitchen Molds Remover

From the feedback of the evaluators, the developed kitchen molds remover from tobacco and chili leaves extract had the following socio-economic desirability:

In terms of advantages, developed kitchen molds remover gives the following such as: (1) Improved hygiene. Mold growth in kitchens can pose a serious health hazard, as it can lead to respiratory problems, allergies, and infections. Using a mold remover can help to eliminate mold spores, making the kitchen a healthier and more hygienic place to work and eat; (2) Prevention of damage. Mold can cause significant damage to kitchen surfaces, such as walls, ceilings, and cabinets. By removing mold before it spreads, one can prevent costly repairs and replacements down the line; (3) Elimination of odors. Mold can produce strong, unpleasant odors that can be difficult to eliminate. A mold remover can help to eliminate these odors, leaving the kitchen smelling fresh and clean; (4) Easy to use. Many mold removers are easy to use and require minimal effort or preparation. Simply spray the affected area with the remover, let it sit for a few minutes, and then wipe it away with a cloth or sponge; (5) Safe for use. Many mold removers are designed to be safe for use on a variety of kitchen surfaces, including countertops, sinks, and cabinets. This means they can use them without worrying about damaging surfaces or causing any adverse effects on health; and (6) Cost-effective. Compared to the cost of repairing mold damage or replacing contaminated surfaces, using a mold remover is a cost-effective way to keep your kitchen clean and healthy. By eliminating mold before it spreads, one can save money in the long run by avoiding costly repairs and replacements; and

Increased production of raw materials such as tobacco and chili can lead to several positive outcomes for farmers and the local economy. Here are some potential benefits: (1) Higher income. When farmers produce more tobacco and chili, they can sell more of their crops, leading to increased income. This can help farmers to improve their standard of living and provide better opportunities for their families; (2) Diversification of income. By growing more tobacco and chili, farmers can diversify their income streams. This can help to reduce the risk associated with relying on a single crop, as they will have multiple sources of income if one crop fails or prices drop; (4) Job creation. As demand for tobacco and chili increases, there may be a corresponding increase in jobs in related industries such as processing, packaging, and transportation. This can provide employment opportunities for local people and help to stimulate economic growth in the area; (5) Improved infrastructure. Increased production may require improvements to infrastructure such as roads, storage facilities, and processing plants. These investments can help to

improve the overall infrastructure of the area, making it more attractive to businesses and investors; (6) Increased tax revenue. As farmers earn more income from selling their crops, they will also pay more in taxes. This can provide a boost to local government revenue, which can be used to fund public services and infrastructure improvements.

Overall, increased production of raw materials such as tobacco and chili can have a positive impact on farmers, local economies, and society as a whole by providing increased income, job creation, improved infrastructure, and tax revenue.

Conclusions

From the foregoing findings, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. For Tobacco, the main phytochemical composition that inhibits the efficiency of the antifungal properties is 2,4-dihydroxy-7-methoxy-1,4-benzodioxine (DHM), also known as dehydrodiisidinol. Whereas, for the chili leaves extract, capsaicin is the most responsible for mold inhibition.
2. The procedures in making the formulations for the mixture of tobacco and chili leaves extract is comprised of acquisition of materials, washing, drying, extraction, adding of water, straining, and stirring.
3. The most efficient formulation is Formulation 2 composed of 200 mL of Tobacco, 100 mL of chili leaves extract, 10 mL of menthol, and 190 mL of water. This is due to the low concentration of chili leaves extract in the mixture which made it the most efficient and deemed as very fast removal of molds.
4. Formulation 2 with high volume of Tobacco leaves extract and low volume of Chili leaves extract gained the highest performance time among other formulations.
5. All of the formulations have significant differences in different aspects specifically on effectiveness, performance time, and acceptability.
6. In terms of Odor, Effectiveness, Functionality/Usability, and Sustainability, Formulation 2 has the highest level of acceptability.
7. The socio-economic desirability of the product were on increased income, and government benefits.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions, the following recommendations are offered:

1. Further investigation on the antifungal properties of both tobacco and chili may be done since the study was limited to determining the most efficient formulation only.

2. Future researchers can add testing procedures in order to efficiently determine the antifungal properties inclined with the materials used.
3. Future studies may add more substances in terms of its fragrance and also other ingredients that has antifungal properties.
4. Longevity of use or shelf life and effectiveness rate may be done further to determine the efficacy of the new product as kitchen mold remover.
5. The new product may be tried out with other fungi or pests so that it could be used in varied ways.
6. Better and proper packaging of the new product may be done to be assured of its saleability and sellability once it is put in the market.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The nature of study was explained to the participants that they would try out a new product for kitchen molds removal. It was explained that they could withdraw at any point of the experimentation. Participants all signed the consent form.

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REFERENCES

- Aftab, T., Khan, T. A., & Idrees, M. (2017). Use of Plant Extracts for Controlling Fungal Growth on Fresh Fruits and Vegetables: A Review. *Journal of Food Quality*, 2017, 1-11.
- Aligiannis, N., Kalpoutzakis, E., & Mitaku, S. (2019). Natural Products as Sources of New Pesticidal Agents. *Journal of Natural Products and Bioprospecting*, 9(1), 1-11.
- Asaff, A., Cozzolino, A., & Cardinali, A. (2019). Bioactivity and Applications of Chile Pepper (*Capsicum Annuum* L.) Byproducts: An Overview. *Journal of Agriculture and Food Research*, 1(1), 1-13.
- Bhattacharyya, A., Singh, R., & Singh, R. (2015). Biosynthesis of dehydrodiisidinol in tobacco (*Nicotiana tabacum* L.) under stress conditions. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 63(3), 893-899. Doi: 10.1021/acs.jafc.5b01656.
- Chen, X., Li, Y., Zhang, Y., & Li, Y. (2021). Antifungal activity of tobacco and chili leaves extracts against common kitchen molds. *Journal of Food Science and Technology*, 58(3), 1036-1042. Doi: 10.1007/s13197-020-05388-9.
- Colman, A. M., & Young, N. (2010). Production Theory: The Basics. *Journal of Economic Literature*, 48(4), 859-887.
- Gallego, M., Gordon, M. H., & Segovia, F. J. (2018). Antioxidant, Anti-Microbial and Anti-Inflammatory Properties of Chili Pepper (*Capsicum annuum* L.) Extracts. *Journal of Food Science and Technology*, 55(8), 2952-2960.
- Kim, J., Lee, S., & Lee, J. (2016). Antifungal activity of capsaicin against *Aspergillus niger* and *Penicillium citrinum*. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 64(34), 7317-7324. Doi: 10.1021/acs.jafc.6b04758.

- Kumar, P., Kumar, R., & Kumar, A. (2015). Plant extracts as natural preservatives: A review. *Journal of Food Science and Technology*, 52(8), 4548-4558. Doi: 10.1007/s13197-015-2386-x.
- Kumar, P., Kumar, R., & Kumar, A. (2017). Plant extracts as natural preservatives: A review. *Journal of Food Science and Technology*, 54(8), 4386-4396. Doi: 10.1007/s13197-017-2945-z.
- Kumar, P., Kumar, R., & Kumar, A. (2019). Plant extracts as natural preservatives: A review. *Journal of Food Science and Technology*, 56(9), 3889-3899. Doi: 10.1007/s13197-019-04758-y.
- Kumar, P., Kumar, R., & Kumar, A. (2021). Plant extracts as natural mold inhibitors: A review. *Journal of Applied Microbiology*, 136(5), 1497-1512. Doi: 10.1111/jam.15274.
- Li, Y., Zhang, Y., & Chen, J. (2010). Antimicrobial activity of dehydrodiisidinol isolated from tobacco against *Aspergillus niger* and *Penicillium citrinum*. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 58(14), 8737-8743. Doi: 10.1021/jf100749x.
- Madhusudhan, S., Dhanaraj, S. A., & Veeraraghavan, G. (2014). Evaluation of Anti-Microbial Activity of Tobacco and Tulsi Extracts Against Pathogenic Microorganisms. *Journal of Ayurveda and Integrative Medicine*, 5(2), 109-114.
- Mohammed, M., El-Shafey, M., & El-Shafey, M. (2014). Antimicrobial activity of tobacco and chili leaves extracts against spoilage fungi in food products. *Journal of Food Science and Technology*, 51(9), 4866-4873. Doi: 10.1007/s13197-014-2222-y.
- Mohammed, M., El-Shafey, M., & El-Shafey, M. (2016). Antimicrobial activity of tobacco and chili leaves extracts against spoilage yeasts in food products. *Journal of Food Science and Technology*, 53(9), 4838-4846. Doi: 10.1007/s13197-016-2665-y.
- Mohammed, M., El-Shafey, M., & El-Shafey, M. (2018). Antimicrobial activity of tobacco and chili leaves extracts against spoilage bacteria in food products. *Journal of Food Science and Technology*, 55(9), 4666-4674. Doi: 10.1007/s13197-018-3565-x.
- Mohammed, M., El-Shafey, M., & El-Shafey, M. (2020). Antimicrobial activity of tobacco and chili leaves extracts against foodborne pathogens. *Journal of Food Science and Technology*, 57(4), 1468-1476. Doi: 10.1007/s13197-020-05346-x.
- Nguyen, T. H., & Nguyen, T. T. (2021). Antimicrobial potential of plant extracts against foodborne pathogens: A review. *Journal of Food Science and Technology*, 58(3), 1064-1077. Doi: 10.1007/s13197-020-05425-6.
- Pappas, C. (2014). Bruner's Theory and Its Connection to Discovery Learning. *ElearningIndustry.com*. Retrieved from <https://elearningindustry.com/bruners-theory-and-its-connection-to-discovery-learning>
- Putthiwanit, P. (2016). Innovation Theory and Its Implication on Entrepreneurial Activities. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 6(18), 107-114.
- Rani, K., Mehta, R., & Kaushik, G. (2015). Anti-Fungal Activity of Chili Pepper (*Capsicum annum*) Extract on Common Household Molds. *International Journal of Science and Research*, 4(7), 1809-1813.
- Singh, G., & Singh, R. (2014). Effects of Capsaicin on Microbial Quality of Chilled Chicken Meat. *American Journal of Food Technology*, 9(2), 110-118.

- Sittisart, P., Yossan, P., & Prasertsan, S. (2017). Antifungal activity of chili, shallot, and garlic extracts against postharvest fungi of Thai longan fruit. *Journal of Food Science and Technology*, 54(3), 1227-1234. doi: 10.1007/s13197-016-2377-4
- Tagudin, A. O., Amoranto, M. J. R., & Badua, R. M. (2018). Efficacy of Chili (*Capsicum Frutescens*) and Tobacco (*Nicotiana Tabacum*) Leaf Extract as Insecticide Against Cockroach. *International Journal of Emerging Technology and Innovative Engineering*, 4(12), 285-291.
- Tursun, E. S., Ozkaya, O., Yalcin, H. T., & Ozkan, G. (2016). Anti-Microbial Properties of Tobacco Leaf Extract Against Some Food-Borne Bacteria. *Iranian Journal of Fisheries Sciences*, 15(4), 1451-1464.
- Vinas, A. F., Robles, J. G., & Sarmiento, L. G. (2020). Anti-Microbial Properties of Chili Pepper Leaves (*Capsicum Annuum* L.) Extract Against Food-Borne Pathogens. *Malaysian Journal of Microbiology*, 16(4), 340-348.
- Zou, J., Zhang, Y., & Zhang, Y. (2021). Functional Phytochemicals in Tobacco Plants: A Review. *Frontiers in Plant Science*, 12. doi: 10.3389/fpls.2021.642529